

Neutronic Analysis of a Small Subcritical Fusion-Fission Hybrid Reactor for Transuranic Transmutation

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803918

ABSTRACT

This work introduces a small subcritical hybrid fusion-fission reactor designed to analyze the transmutation characteristics of four reprocessed fuel types: oxygen-based (TRU-Th and TRU-DU) and nitrogen-based (TRU-Th and TRU-DU). The small subcritical hybrid reactor is based on the SEALER reactor, a fast-spectrum, lead-cooled SMR, whose design characteristics favor the proposed adaptation. Steady-state analyses of the reprocessed fuels show similarities in the behavior and distribution of neutron flux in the core when compared to the UO₂ fuel of the original SEALER design. Furthermore, initial burnup evaluations with reprocessed oxygen-based fuels suggest that their burnup can be extended beyond the initially simulated 5 years, despite the high subcriticality achieved. This condition ensures the new design's safety. The simulations were conducted using the Serpent code, version 2.1.33, with the neutron cross-section data library ENDF/B-VIII.0 and the decay and fission product production data library ENDF/B-VII.1.

Keywords: Hybrid Systems, SMRs, Transmutation, Reprocessed Fuels

1. INTRODUCTION

The hybrid reactor can be considered an attractive actinide burner for transmuting transuranic nuclear waste and breeding fissile material [1,2]. The availability of high-energy neutrons from an external source, coupled with the system (such as neutrons produced by spallation or fusion reactions), enables transuranic burning in a subcritical operating mode, rendering such systems inherently safe.

Several proposals for hybrid reactors have been studied. However, the most developed concepts are the fusion-fission hybrid (FFH) reactors and the Accelerator Driven Systems (ADS) [1,2]. The FFH is a subcritical nuclear fission reactor supported by an additional source of fusion neutrons generated in the plasma (²H-²H, ²H-³H, ³H-³H, etc.), confined by magnetic fields or inertial confinement. An ADS consists of a high-power proton accelerator, a heavy metal spallation target that produces neutrons when bombarded by the high-power beam, and a subcritical core that is neutronicly coupled to the spallation target, i.e, ADS-fission hybrid system.

One of the significant obstacles to constructing these reactors is the development of materials capable of withstanding the hostile environments to which they will be exposed due to the high temperatures and intense bombardment by high-energy particles, conditions created by the technology of the external neutron source [1,2]. In addition, these machines are designed as large projects, consequently increasing their cost and construction time.

In contrast, SMRs are characterized by their reduced size and modularity, aiming to reduce manufacturing costs and to optimize construction and implementation time for these reactors [3]. Currently, several types of SMRs, such as fast-neutron spectrum reactors (fast SMRs), are under development [3]. Among them, the SEALER [4], an acronym for Swedish Advanced Lead Reactor, a small modular fast-neutron reactor cooled by lead, has design characteristics that are favorable for

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adaptation to a small subcritical hybrid reactor. The lead-cooled core composition and geometry maintain a hardened neutron spectrum, which is necessary for the transmutation of transuranic isotopes by fission in reprocessed fuel. Thus, this work aims to evaluate the burnup of reprocessed fuels in a small subcritical hybrid reactor based on SEALER, using a fusion neutron spectrum characteristic of the plasma parameters from the tokamak reactor ITER [5,6]. To this end, the initial behavior of four fuels proposed for analysis—oxygen-based (TRU, Th) and (TRU, DU); and nitrogen-based (TRU, Th) and (TRU, DU)—is investigated in conjunction with the UO_2 fuel, initially designed for the SEALER core.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Small Hybrid Reactor Design

To utilize the SEALER core as a small subcritical reactor coupled with an external neutron source, the central fuel assembly was removed and replaced with liquid lead, which was used in the original project as both a coolant and a reflector, as shown in Figure 1. All other structures in the reactor core remain unchanged, including the control rods, shutdown rods, reflectors, and shielding assemblies, as specified by the main design parameters outlined in Table I. This work simulates the external neutron source with an energy spectrum of fusion neutrons produced in ^2H - ^3H reactions, from a hybrid fusion-fission system based on the ITER reactor [6]. Furthermore, the UO_2 fuel enriched to 19.75% from the original SEALER design is replaced in the new core by four types of reprocessed fuels to be analyzed: (TRU, Th) and (TRU, DU) oxygen-based fuels, and (TRU, Th) and (TRU, DU) nitrogen-based fuels.

Figure 1. The proposed model for a small subcritical hybrid reactor based on SEALER. The image on the left shows an axial view of the core, with the control and shutdown rods withdrawn; the image on the right shows its radial view, identifying the location of each assembly.

Table I. Core design parameters of a small subcritical hybrid reactor based on SEALER [4].

Item	Value	Temperature
External Source Radius	6.926 cm	684 K
External Source Height	110.6 cm	
Fuel assemblies	18	750 K
Fuel pins per assembly	91	
Burnup control assemblies	12	684 K
B_4C rods/burnup control assembly	19	
Shutdown assemblies	6	684 K
(W, Re) $^{10}\text{B}_2$ rods/shutdown assembly	7	

Reflector assemblies	24	684 K
YSZ rods/reflector assembly	37	
Shield assemblies	24	684 K
¹⁰B₄C rods/shield assembly	19	
Core barrel inner diameter	170.8 cm	-
Primary vessel outer diameter	274.8 cm	-
Primary vessel height	600.0 cm	-

2.2. Fuel Composition

The reprocessed fuel used for transmutation analyses is derived from spent fuel from the Angra I reactor, a PWR, which was initially enriched to 3.1% and had a total burnup of 33 GWd/t [7]. The GANEX reprocessing method [8] was employed to obtain the reprocessed fuel, due to its non-proliferation characteristics and the recovery of minor actinides, which are targeted for transmutation. The recovery factors used in the GANEX reprocessing method are the same as those in [9]. After obtaining the actinides and some fission products described in Table II, this reprocessed fuel matrix is spiked with thorium and depleted uranium, based on nitrogen and oxygen, resulting in the four different compositions initially simulated in this work, as shown in Table II below. The final percentage of fissile material in each fuel is specified based on the subcritical multiplication factor of the core, k_s , approaching 0.98 [10], with the control and shutdown rods completely removed (Figure 1).

Table II. Initial composition (BOL) of the four fuels simulated in this work.

Nuclides	Weight Fraction			
	(TRU, Th)O ₂	(TRU, DU)O ₂	(TRU, Th)N	(TRU, DU)N
²³² Th	6.79201 × 10 ⁻¹	-	7.29085 × 10 ⁻¹	-
²³³ U	7.13957 × 10 ⁻¹³	5.79922 × 10 ⁻¹³	7.64243 × 10 ⁻¹³	6.17994 × 10 ⁻¹³
²³⁴ U	2.94653 × 10 ⁻⁶	2.39337 × 10 ⁻⁶	3.15407 × 10 ⁻⁶	2.55049 × 10 ⁻⁶
²³⁵ U	1.53349 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.56232 × 10 ⁻³	1.64150 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.67503 × 10 ⁻³
²³⁶ U	7.83900 × 10 ⁻⁵	6.36735 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.39112 × 10 ⁻⁵	6.78536 × 10 ⁻⁵
²³⁷ U	2.02213 × 10 ⁻⁹	1.64251 × 10 ⁻⁹	2.16455 × 10 ⁻⁹	1.75034 × 10 ⁻⁹
²³⁸ U	1.86417 × 10 ⁻²	7.32582 × 10 ⁻¹	1.99547 × 10 ⁻²	7.85738 × 10 ⁻¹
²³⁷ Np	8.61670 × 10 ⁻³	6.99905 × 10 ⁻³	9.22360 × 10 ⁻³	7.45854 × 10 ⁻³
²³⁸ Np	2.55601 × 10 ⁻⁷	2.07616 × 10 ⁻⁷	2.73604 × 10 ⁻⁷	2.21246 × 10 ⁻⁷
²³⁹ Np	1.61386 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.31088 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.72753 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.39694 × 10 ⁻⁵
²³⁸ Pu	3.51020 × 10 ⁻³	2.85121 × 10 ⁻³	3.75743 × 10 ⁻³	3.03839 × 10 ⁻³
²³⁹ Pu	9.19174 × 10 ⁻²	7.46613 × 10 ⁻²	9.83915 × 10 ⁻²	7.95629 × 10 ⁻²
²⁴⁰ Pu	3.14230 × 10 ⁻²	2.55238 × 10 ⁻²	3.36362 × 10 ⁻²	2.71994 × 10 ⁻²
²⁴¹ Pu	2.95456 × 10 ⁻²	2.39988 × 10 ⁻²	3.16266 × 10 ⁻²	2.55744 × 10 ⁻²
²⁴² Pu	1.11659 × 10 ⁻²	9.06965 × 10 ⁻³	1.19523 × 10 ⁻²	9.66507 × 10 ⁻³
²⁴¹ Am	2.84704 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.31255 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.04757 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.46437 × 10 ⁻⁵
²⁴² Am	5.23949 × 10 ⁻⁸	4.25586 × 10 ⁻⁸	5.60852 × 10 ⁻⁸	4.53525 × 10 ⁻⁸
²⁴³ Am	2.13532 × 10 ⁻³	1.73445 × 10 ⁻³	2.28572 × 10 ⁻³	1.84831 × 10 ⁻³
²⁴² Cm	8.86525 × 10 ⁻⁶	7.20093 × 10 ⁻⁶	9.48965 × 10 ⁻⁶	7.67367 × 10 ⁻⁶
²⁴⁴ Cm	1.01631 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.25513 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.08789 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.79708 × 10 ⁻⁶
²⁴⁵ Cm	3.53648 × 10 ⁻⁷	2.87256 × 10 ⁻⁶	3.78557 × 10 ⁻⁷	3.06115 × 10 ⁻⁷
¹⁴³ Nd	2.34513 × 10 ⁻³	1.90487 × 10 ⁻³	2.51031 × 10 ⁻³	2.02993 × 10 ⁻³
¹⁵⁰ Sm	4.70283 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.81995 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.03406 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.07072 × 10 ⁻⁴
¹⁵³ Eu	1.00003 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.12291 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.07047 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.65618 × 10 ⁻⁵
¹⁴ N	-	-	5.66463 × 10 ⁻²	5.55900 × 10 ⁻²
¹⁶ O	1.20629 × 10 ⁻¹	1.18531 × 10 ⁻¹	-	-
Total	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000
Fissile Material (%)	13.83	11.37	13.80	11.31

2.3. Definition of The Neutrons External Source

The fusion neutron spectrum used as external source particles in the small hybrid reactor is taken from an FFH reactor model with materials and plasma dimensions based on the ITER reactor, with fusion power and plasma chamber volume set to 500 MWth and 837.0 m³ [6]. This spectrum is measured at the position of the transmutation layer of the FFH reactor, as shown in Figure 2a. The 14.1 MeV neutrons produced in the fusion reactions between ²H and ³H are represented by a Gaussian fusion energy spectrum (Equation 1), whose plasma temperature is 10 keV. The parameters *a* and *b* correspond to the width ΔE above *b*, where the exponential value is equivalent to e^{-1} and the average energy, in MeV, respectively. Both the geometry and the spectrum of the fusion neutrons from the FFH reactor are modeled using MCNP6.2 [11].

$$p(E) = C \exp \left[- \left(\frac{E - b}{a} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. a) Fusion neutron source in the plasma and transmutation layer (in red) of the FFH reactor; b) Neutron spectrum of fusion and the target at the center of the small subcritical reactor based on SEALER, for the four different simulated fuels.

With the insertion of the fusion neutron spectrum at the reactor core, new neutron spectra are obtained, due both to the new geometry and composition of the materials in the core of the new system, and to the different compositions of the fuels, as shown in Figure 2b. It can be observed that the characteristic peak of fusion neutrons, at $E_n = 14.1 \text{ MeV}$, is also present in the new target spectra, and the influence of the fuels is verified by analyzing differences in albedo values calculated on the target's cylindrical surface.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Steady-State Analysis

Initially, the conditions of the core in the BOL loaded with the four reprocessed fuels were analyzed and compared with the initial design core of SEALER, loaded with UO₂ enriched to 19.75%. The simulations were conducted using Serpent 2.1.33 [12] and the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear cross-section

library [13], at the operating temperature (Table I). Table III presents the values of the multiplication factor, the effective fraction of delayed neutrons (β_{eff}), and the shutdown margin (S_{dm}).

Table III. Initial BOL parameters for the original SEALER reactor design and its modified proposal with reprocessed fuels.

	k_s	β_{eff} (pcm)	S_{dm} (pcm)*
UO₂ Reference [14]	1.04712**	752	-3000
(TRU, Th)O ₂	0.98017 ± 0.00003	322	-1496
(TRU, DU)O ₂	0.98014 ± 0.00003	405	-1525
(TRU, Th)N	0.98008 ± 0.00004	328	-1528
(TRU, DU)N	0.97997 ± 0.00003	416	-1582

* For the subcritical core, $S_{dm} = 0.98 - k_{s_{dm}}$, where $k_{s_{dm}}$ corresponds to the subcriticality value with the control and shutdown rods fully inserted.

**System criticality eigenvalue (k_{eff}).

For reprocessed fuels, the calculation of the multiplication factor must take into account both the multiplication caused by neutrons from the external source and by fission neutrons, and is therefore different from the effective multiplication factor obtained for the original nucleus. Thus, the subcritical multiplication, or the subcritical multiplication factor k_s , is calculated according to the equation below,

$$k_s = \frac{F}{F + S_e} \quad (2)$$

where F is the total number of fission neutrons, and S_e is the total number of neutrons from the external source. As previously indicated, $k_s \sim 0.98$ was stipulated as the initial subcriticality value for the four reprocessed fuels. Therefore, even the large discrepancy in the β_{eff} and S_{dm} values of the transuranic fuels compared to the original UO₂ fuel will not affect the safety of the core in its new configuration, since it starts from a considerable subcriticality of ~ -2000 pcm. The initial presence of plutonium explains the low β_{eff} value of the transuranic fuels.

Analyses of the neutron flux behavior in the reactor core were also conducted. Figure 3 shows the spectrum of the transuranic fuels compared to that of the UO₂ fuel. Except for the characteristic peak of the external neutron source, the behavior of the fuels is quite similar, especially those based on oxygen, which exhibit two small valleys at the ~ 0.4 and ~ 1.0 MeV points, coinciding with the first two resonance peaks of the total microscopic cross-section of ¹⁶O, as shown in the graph.

The distribution of neutron flux along the radial and axial positions is shown in Figure 4. With the addition of external neutrons to the core, the particle population of the respective transuranic fuels is considerably larger than that of UO₂ fuel, with a 27% difference. However, additional implications related to core safety also arise from the observed behavior, requiring further analysis, including power distribution and material damage.

3.2. First Results of the Burnup

Figure 5 and Table IV present some initial burnup results of oxygen-based fuels (TRU, Th) and (TRU, DU). For this analysis, the nominal power of 8 MWth from the original SEALER project was maintained, thus establishing an average neutron generation rate from the external source (\overline{PGR}_{ES}) equal to:

$$\overline{PGR}_{ES} = \frac{(1/19) \cdot 8000000 \text{ W}}{\bar{E}_n \cdot 1.6022 \times 10^{-13} \frac{\text{J}}{\text{MeV}}} \cong 2.94 \times 10^{18} \text{ neutrons/s} \quad (3)$$

where \bar{E}_n is the average neutron energy from the external source of each fuel, with values ranging from 0.83 to 0.95 MeV (neutron current spectrum at the target, Figure 2). Fuels were burned continuously for 5 years at a total burn rate of 5.99 MWd/kgHM.

As shown in Figure 5, the burnup of the two fuels is quite similar, with both reaching subcriticality of ~ 0.96 at the end of the period. The most significant differences are evident in the conversion ratios, transmutation rates, and mass variations of the actinides present in BOL. Since the fuels are spiked with thorium and depleted uranium, the consumption and production of some isotopes, such as ²³²Th, ²³³U,

^{238}U , and ^{239}Pu , vary depending on the dilution material. Despite $(\text{TRU}, \text{DU})\text{O}_2$ exhibiting higher production of fissile material, transuranic transmutation, especially by fission, occurs at a lower rate than in $(\text{TRU}, \text{Th})\text{O}_2$. The calculation of TR^{TRU} and TR^{MA} includes both fission and neutron capture transmutations in their isotope consumption. In contrast, the values for $TR_{fission}^{TRU}$ are calculated using the relative probability that neutron absorption by nuclide i leads to fission, as shown in equation 4 below:

$$TR_{fission} = \sum_j^N \sum_{i=0}^T \left(\frac{1}{1 + \alpha_{j,i_1}} \frac{m_{j,i_1}}{t_{i_1}} - \frac{1}{1 + \alpha_{j,i_0}} \frac{m_{j,i_0}}{t_{i_0}} \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha_{j,i}$ and $m_{j,i}$ are the values for the capture-fission ratio and mass of nuclide j at time t_i .

Figure 3. Neutron flux spectrum in the active core of the small hybrid subcritical reactor based on SEALER and the original SEALER core.

Figure 4. Radial and axial neutron flux for the analyzed fuels.

Figure 5. Subcritical multiplication factor as a function of burnup for (TRU, Th)O₂ and (TRU, DU)O₂ fuels.

Table IV. Values for the initial and final subcritical multiplication factor (k_s^i and k_s^f), conversion ratio (CR), average transmutation rate of transuranic and minor actinides (TR^{TRU} and TR^{MA}), transmutation rate per fission of transuranic ($TR_{fission}^{TRU}$) and mass variation (Δm) of oxygen-based fuels.

	(TRU, Th)O ₂	(TRU, DU)O ₂
k_s^i	0.98018	0.98014
k_s^f	0.95766	0.95746
CR	0.85752	0.87005
TR^{TRU*} (g/day)	8.76516	7.27651
TR^{MA} (g/day)	8.65950	6.53207
$TR_{fission}^{TRU}$ (g/day)	1.59685	1.14329
$\Delta m = m^f - m^i$ (kg)		
²³² Th	-1.193×10^1	5.159×10^{-8}
²³³ U	1.070×10^1	3.390×10^{-5}
²³⁴ U	3.862×10^{-1}	2.866×10^{-1}
²³⁵ U	1.579×10^{-2}	-1.801×10^{-1}
²³⁶ U	4.450×10^{-2}	9.831×10^{-2}
²³⁷ U	2.955×10^{-5}	8.886×10^{-4}
²³⁸ U	-3.187×10^{-1}	-1.323×10^1
²³⁷ Np	-7.268×10^{-1}	-5.475×10^{-1}
²³⁸ Np	3.493×10^{-4}	4.619×10^{-4}
²³⁹ Np	-4.289×10^{-2}	-1.368×10^{-2}
²³⁸ Pu	9.083×10^{-2}	1.690×10^{-1}
²³⁹ Pu	-1.025×10^1	1.208×10^0
²⁴⁰ Pu	2.474×10^{-1}	5.042×10^{-1}
²⁴¹ Pu	-1.934×10^1	-1.588×10^1
²⁴² Pu	1.258×10^{-1}	1.549×10^{-1}
²⁴¹ Am	1.586×10^1	1.276×10^1
²⁴² Am	1.191×10^{-4}	1.333×10^{-4}
²⁴³ Am	1.079×10^{-2}	1.897×10^{-2}
²⁴² Cm	2.217×10^{-2}	2.446×10^{-2}
²⁴⁴ Cm	1.409×10^{-1}	1.367×10^{-1}
²⁴⁵ Cm	9.614×10^{-4}	1.079×10^{-3}
FP**	1.034×10^1	1.037×10^1

* Except for fissile isotopes: ²³³U, ²³⁵U, ²³⁹Pu, ²⁴¹Pu; and fertile isotopes: ²³²Th, ²³⁸U and ²⁴⁰Pu.

** Fission products considered according to reference [15].

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work aims to evaluate the transmutation capacity of a small subcritical hybrid reactor based on SEALER, loaded with different reprocessed fuels. To this end, initial analyses of these fuels, namely (TRU, Th)O₂, (TRU, DU)O₂, (TRU, Th)N, and (TRU, DU)N, for the BOL state, were initially conducted, along with the SEALER core in its original design, loaded with UO₂ fuel enriched to 19.75%.

The subcriticality of the modified SEALER core is established at a value close to 0.98, and therefore, the compositions of the four reprocessed fuels present different percentages of fissile material. It also produces different spectra for the external neutron source, which vary due to differences in scattering from the fusion neutrons.

The subcriticality of the core, approximately -2000 pcm, also allows for lower values of β_{eff} and S_{dm} , given the -3000 pcm shutdown margin of the original SEALER design. In burnup analyses, (TRU,

Th) O_2 exhibits higher transmutation rates, especially fission transmutation rates, the parameter targeted in this work.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors express their sincere gratitude to the Brazilian research funding agencies CNPq, CAPES, CNEN, and FAPEMIG for their support.

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